

	Undergraduate student	Graduate Student	Professional
Piano technique	<p>Acquiring tools for good sound, accuracy, color, articulation, pedaling.</p> <p>Still learning how to practice efficiently.</p>	<p>Advancing interpretative skills, developing a technique for virtuosity and longevity.</p> <p>Increasing efficiency; able to do more with less time.</p>	<p>Knows own strengths well, understands how much time it will take to prepare for any gig/assignment.</p> <p>More able to avoid injuries of overuse or poor habits/training.</p>
Sight-reading	<p>Will benefit from daily sightreading practice of simpler songs and instrumental pieces.</p> <p>May not be ready for public sight-reading experiences.</p>	<p>Will benefit from daily sightreading practice of more advanced literature including opera arias.</p> <p>May be ready to read in vocal and choral rehearsals or play things on short notice.</p>	<p>Has experience reading open scores, full scores, possibly figured bass.</p> <p>Will be able to handle sight-reading in the course of employment.</p>
Musicianship	<p>Developing understanding of form, style, phrasing, and ornamentation practices of different eras.</p> <p>Needs substantial rehearsal and mentorship to prepare for public performance.</p>	<p>Learning the specific skills and needs of various vocal and instrumental partners.</p> <p>Needs substantial rehearsal and some mentorship to prepare for public performance.</p>	<p>Has experience with standard rep of many instrument(s) and voice types.</p> <p>Minimal rehearsal needed before public performance.</p>
Ensemble	<p>Developing the ability to listen and “follow” partners without hesitating or anticipating.</p>	<p>Developing the ability to follow a conductor.</p> <p>Vocal: developing the ability to keep ensemble with sung texts in a variety of languages.</p> <p>Instrumental: developing the ability to respond</p>	<p>Can anticipate a partner’s direction of phrase and rubato based, knows instinctively when to lead/follow/help/wait.</p>

		specifically to the articulation and phrasing of various instruments.	
Balance	<p>May still be limited in ability to affect balance as piano technique is refining.</p>	<p>Improvement in understanding piano voicing and pedaling, along with elements of specific voices and instruments that affect balance.</p> <p>Will need feedback about balance for rehearsal and performance.</p>	<p>Experienced with vocalists and instrumentalists at various stages of development and can adjust to their needs.</p> <p>Little to no outside feedback about balance is necessary.</p>
Languages	<p>May have no experience with a second language.</p> <p>Should be encouraged to begin language study if not required in the curriculum.</p>	<p>Increasing familiarity with language and diction study, International Phonetic Alphabet.</p>	<p>Expected competency in French, German, Italian lyric diction, perhaps other languages; understanding of prosody.</p>
Coaching Skills	<p>Learning to rehearse with partners; will benefit from oversight/mentorship.</p> <p>Rare for a pianist at this level to have the necessary competencies to lead the learning of others.</p>	<p>Observing teachers, coaches, playing voice lessons and masterclasses, beginning to coach young singers.</p> <p>Will benefit from early opportunities to music direct or lead groups, sectionals, choirs, with mentorship.</p>	<p>Ability to coach singers of all levels with honesty; actively working professionally as a coach; identifying areas of specialization.</p>
Opera	<p>Beginning to gain exposure to solo bel canto singing and style, learning first opera arias with undergraduate singers.</p> <p>Oversight and mentorship are essential.</p>	<p>Learning repertoire, initial involvement as a pianist/coach for school/young artist productions.</p> <p>Preparation time and mentorship for each new activity are essential.</p>	<p>Has experience as a rehearsal pianist and coach.</p> <p>May begin to fill other roles such as language coach, assistant conductor, prompter, conductor, administrator, program coordinator, etc.</p>

Musical Theater	Participating in high school and community shows, listening to pop music.	Gaining deeper knowledge of production process and protocol, ability to play a variety of popular styles. May develop skills in arranging, transcribing, lead sheet/Nashville, with oversight and feedback.	Can run efficient rehearsals for a variety of levels. Establishing affiliations with companies and performing groups.
Recital	In addition to recitals required for the degree, creating opportunities to perform in local venues as a way to develop musical partnerships and increase independence. Will need substantial rehearsal and mentorship.	In addition to recitals required for the degree, exploring a wide variety of partnerships and repertoire, entering duo competitions, exploring summer programs with a recital emphasis. Working with less mentorship and in shorter time frames. Care must be taken to ensure balance and fairness of student workloads and evaluation.	Curating own gigs, being hired regionally or nationally, maybe beginning to specialize.
Audition accompanying	Not expected at the undergraduate level. If any, planned and rehearsed ahead of time.	Also rare at this level. If any, best with repertoire provided in advance and with short rehearsals.	Playing collegiate and young artist program auditions, competitions. Able to sight-read or successfully execute with little to no rehearsal is essential.
Choral	May have choral accompanying experience from high school, or may need mentorship. Choral repertoire should	Developing the ability to read open scores, play parts in rehearsal. Increased skill in following a	Experience in responding to a variety of conductors. Ability to change articulation and dynamics to support

	be chosen with the individual's abilities in mind, and provided in advance.	conductor, playing pieces on short notice.	the conductor's goals.
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